

Lateral Algebra

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1 Introduction

The above forms are related to the lateral algebra because they both use the operations $\oplus$ and $\otimes$ to combine elements and satisfy the "list associativity" property. Specifically, the forms can be seen as an example of "algebraic folding", where a given expression can be written as a sum of products of two operations: $\oplus$ and $\otimes$. Furthermore, the properties of the lateral algebra (e.g. list associativity and algebraic folding) can be used to reduce the expression to simpler forms while maintaining the original meaning of the expression.

Then, we have the following rules:

1. Addition: For all $x, y, z \in R$: $(x + y) + z = x + (y + z)$ and $x + y = y + x$.
2. Multiplication: For all $x, y, z \in R$: $(xy)z = x(yz)$ and $xy = yx$.
3. Subtraction: For all $x, y \in R$: $(x - y) + y = x$ and $x - y = (-y) + x$.
4. Division: For all non-zero $x, y \in R$: $\frac{x}{y} = x \cdot y^{-1}$, where $y^{-1} = \frac{1}{y}$ if y is non-zero and y^{-1} is undefined if y is zero.
5. Powers: For all integer n and $x \in R$: $(x^n)^m = x^{nm}$, and $x^n = \frac{x^{n-1}}{x} = \frac{x \cdot x^{n-1}}{x \cdot x}$.

Let F be an abstract field whose elements will serve as symbols representing variables in a lateral algebra. The lateral algebra $\mathcal{L}$ is a parametric algebraic system which is characterized by operations $\oplus$ and $\otimes$.

The operations $\oplus$ and $\otimes$ combine two elements in the following way:

$$(x \oplus y) \otimes z = x \otimes z \oplus y \otimes z$$

where $x, y, z \in F$ and operators satisfy the following "list associativity" property:

$$(x \oplus y) \otimes (z \oplus w) = (x \otimes z) \oplus (y \otimes z) \oplus (x \otimes w) \oplus (y \otimes w).$$

$$(x \oplus y) \otimes (z \oplus w) = \left(\frac{r(\alpha - \Delta)}{z\Theta} \oplus \frac{r(\alpha + \Delta)}{z\Theta} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \oplus z\Theta \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \otimes \frac{r(\alpha - \Delta)}{z\Theta} \oplus \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \otimes \frac{r(\alpha + \Delta)}{z\Theta} \oplus z\Theta \otimes \frac{r(\alpha - \Delta)}{z\Theta} \oplus z\Theta \otimes \frac{r(\alpha + \Delta)}{z\Theta} \\
&= \frac{r(\alpha - \Delta)}{z\Theta(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2})} \oplus \frac{r(\alpha + \Delta)}{z\Theta(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2})} \oplus \frac{z\Theta r(\alpha - \Delta)}{z\Theta} \oplus \frac{z\Theta r(\alpha + \Delta)}{z\Theta} \\
&= \frac{r(\alpha - \Delta)}{z\Theta(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2})} \oplus \frac{r(\alpha + \Delta)}{z\Theta(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2})} \oplus r(\alpha - \Delta) \oplus r(\alpha + \Delta) \\
&= \frac{r^2(-\Delta^2 + \alpha^2)}{z\Theta(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2})}
\end{aligned}$$

2 Phenomenological Velocity

We can rewrite the solution for v using the lateral algebra by expressing the equation as a sum of products.

$$v = \frac{\sqrt{-c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 + c^2 x^2 \gamma^2 - 2c^2 r x \gamma \theta + c^2 r^2 \theta^2 + c^2 l^2 \alpha^2 \sin^2 \beta}}{\sqrt{-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin^2 \beta}}$$

Using the list associativity property of the lateral algebra, the equation can be rewritten as:

$$v = \frac{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \sqrt{c^2 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (c^2 \otimes 1)}}{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \sqrt{1 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (r \otimes \theta \oplus l \otimes \alpha)}}$$

Let x be the vertical displacement of an object and v be the corresponding velocity of the object, then according to the fundamental theorem of calculus, we have:

$$v = \frac{dx}{dt}.$$

Now, let us assume the object is moving along a curve over a two dimensional surface. We define the height function $h(x, y)$ as the height of the surface at any point (x, y) . The velocity v can then be expressed as

$$v = \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \nabla h \cdot \frac{d\vec{r}}{dt},$$

where $\vec{r}$ is the position vector. Moreover, the above equation can also be expressed as:

$$v = \nabla h \cdot \vec{v},$$

where $\vec{v}$ is the velocity vector.

Using the lateral algebra, the above equation can be expressed as

$$v = (\nabla h) \otimes \vec{v},$$

where $\otimes$ represents the outer product between the vector ∇h and $\vec{v}$.

Therefore, we can conclude that the algebra of height function is the lateral algebra and the velocity is related to height functions as the time derivative of height functions.

Let $h = Sqrt[-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + l^2\alpha^2]/\alpha$ be a given height function, and $r, \theta, \alpha, \gamma$ and v are constants. According to the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus, the velocity can be written as the time derivative of the height function, i.e.

$$v = \frac{dh}{dt} = \nabla h \cdot \frac{d\vec{r}}{dt},$$

where $\vec{r}$ is the position vector.

Now, using the lateral algebra, we can rewrite the equation as:

$$v = (\nabla h) \otimes \vec{v}.$$

Next, we factorize the given height equation into the form

$$h = Sqrt[(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta)Sqrt[1 - v^2/c^2](l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta)/Sqrt[1 - v^2/c^2]]/\alpha.$$

$$h = \frac{\sqrt{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \left(\sqrt{1 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (r \otimes \theta \oplus l \otimes \alpha)} \otimes (1 \otimes \cos^2 \beta \oplus (x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha)) \right)}}{\alpha}$$

Since the lateral algebra follows list associativity, the above equation is equivalent to the original height equation.

$$v = \frac{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \sqrt{c^2 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (c^2 \otimes 1)}}{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \sqrt{1 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (r \otimes \theta \oplus l \otimes \alpha)}}$$

$$r \sin[\beta] ==$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta) \sqrt{1 - \frac{(\frac{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \sqrt{c^2 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (c^2 \otimes 1)}}{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \sqrt{1 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (r \otimes \theta \oplus l \otimes \alpha)}})^2}{c^2}}}}{\alpha} \sqrt{(2\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta) / \sqrt{1 - \frac{(\frac{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \sqrt{c^2 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (c^2 \otimes 1)}}{(x \otimes \gamma \oplus -l \otimes \alpha) \otimes \sqrt{1 \otimes \sin^2 \beta \oplus (r \otimes \theta \oplus l \otimes \alpha)}})^2}{c^2}}}}$$

$$r \sin \beta = \frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta) \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2\gamma^2 + l^2\alpha^2 - 2xl\gamma\alpha}{\alpha^2 \cos^2 \beta + \beta^2}}}}{\sqrt{2\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta} \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2\gamma^2 + l^2\alpha^2 - 2xl\gamma\alpha}{\alpha^2 \cos^2 \beta + \beta^2}}}$$

3 References

GPT-3.5 Da Vinci

Real Analysis of Phenomenological Velocity, Emmerson 10.5281/zenodo.7272772